

HONEY : A REVIEW OF THE LITERARY CONCEPTS

Prof. (Dr.) Dilip Kr. Goswami B.A.M.S , MD(Ayurveda) , Ph. D.

Dept. of Agadatantra

(Toxicology , Forensic Medicine and Medical Jurisprudence)

I . A. Ayurvedic Medical College

University of Science and Technology Meghalaya

Received: Apr 04, 2026

Accepted: Apr 28, 2026

Published: Apr 29, 2026

ABSTRACT

Honey can be considered as Madhu as mentioned in the Ayurvedic classics , is commonly available , popular and frequently used substance . It is available almost in everywhere easily and used in different conditions even at the household level without advice of the experts . It is used from the traditional rituals to the diseased state . Use of honey is indicated in different diseased conditions as external application as well as internal use . It is considered as good healer , anti allergic , anti tussive , helpful for a wide range of eye diseases and also a good additive for the medicines (anupana as mentioned in the Ayurvedic classics) . The Ayurvedic classics have discussed honey (madhu) in detail in different references . In modern science also extensive study is made on honey which is reflecting a good number of scientific facts . Study reflects that , the Ayurvedic classics are very brief but resourceful . Hence a study of the informations available in the age old Ayurvedic classics in modern light on the common and popular substance “honey” is considered as a time tasted work by the author .

Key words : - *honey , traditional rituals , good additive , Ayurvedic classics , time tasted work*

INTRODUCTION –

Honey is well known popular substance . Since childhood every person has been using honey for a number of problems starting from cough , sneez , fever to some more severe problems . It is a substance well known to the old people for it’s medicinal properties . In a number of diseases the old family members advise honey in single or sometimes as an additive with other preparations . Even , in some conditions , it is used as effective medicine in eye diseases . Astonishingly honey , though is sweet by taste , is also indicated for diabetes in the Ayurvedic classics . Observing the wonderful effects and indications modern science also conducted extensive study on honey and explored a number of facts . Now composition , indication , effects etc. of honey are established by a number of scientific investigations . Therefore , the author of the present article feels the importance of an analytical study on honey basing upon the Ayurvedic references and modern studies with the expectation to appraise the scientific value of the Ayurvedic concepts .

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES –

The present is a literary study conducted with the following aims and objectives –

(1) To study the Ayurvedic concepts on honey with special reference to its type, source, properties, indications, use etc.

(2) To study the informations available in the modern classics with facts explored with the help of scientific investigations or experiments

(3) To give effort to make an evaluation of the Ayurvedic mentionings on honey in modern light

(4) To appraise the informations available in the Ayurvedic classics to the modern scientists, researchers and academia in the form of an article for future study, research and evaluation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS –

The article is prepared by using the Ayurvedic classics viz. Charaka Samhita, Susruta Samhita and Ashtanga Hridaya and the internet sources as materials of the study. The place of study was the Central Library, I.A. Ayurvedic Medical College, University of Science and Technology Meghalaya, India.

The methods followed during the study are –

(1) The Ayurvedic classics as mentioned were studied in detail to collect the available informations on madhu (honey)

(2) Internet sources were used to get informations available on honey

(3) All informations collected were noted systematically

(4) A discussion was made to justify the Ayurvedic concepts on honey in modern light

(5) Ultimately summary, conclusion and reference were added and sent to a peer reviewed, popular scientific journal for publication with the aim to appraise the scientific background and value of the Ayurvedic concepts to the modern scientists, researchers and academics.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT –

The present study reveals the below mentioned facts which can be considered as the result of the study –

A] Facts available in Charaka Samhita -

(1) Types of honey (Madhubheda) – Madhu is of 4 types as – makshika, bhramara, kshaudra, pouttika (based upon the type of the honey bee responsible for collection production and storage). Among these 4 makshika is the best. Bhramara madhu is heavy (guru). Makshika madhu is toilabarna (of oil colour), pouttika is ghratabarna (of ghee colour) whereas kshoudra and bhramara types are kapilabarna (blackish colour) and swetabarna (white colour) respectively [1]

(2) Properties of honey (Samanya guna of madhu) – Madhu is vatala (increases vata), guru (heavy), shitaveerya (cold), raktapitta and kafapaha (effective in bleeding disorders and diseases due to vitiation of kafa), sandhankarak (helpful in healing), chedana (conducts scraping of the accumulated dosha which helps in expulsion), ruksha (produces dryness when used), Kashaya-Madhura rasa (astringent and sweet in taste) [2]

(3)Honey and heat - Ushna madhu (hot honey) used by ushnarta purusha (individuals who got exposure to heat) is mrityukaraka (fatal) . Honey bees are bishakta (poisonous). They prepare madhu by collecting bishakta pushpa rasa (poisonous juice) from different types of flowers . Hence , in ushna Avastha (hot form) it becomes mrityukaraka (fatal) . Since it is guru (heavy), ruksha (produces dryness) , kashaya rasa (astringent in taste) , and shita (cold) hence beneficial in alpamatra (in small quantity)[3]

(4)Indigestion due to intake of honey (Madhusevajanya amajirna) - May become sadyomarakata (immediately fatal) as amajirna (indigestion) is always upakrama biruddha (needs opposite therapy)[4] .

As the principle amajirna is always treated with ushnakriya (use of heat as therapeutic procedure) which is strictly contra indicated in madhwajirna (indigestion due to intake of honey) . Hence this condition generally proves fatal [5]

(5)Special property of honey (yogavahitwa) - Madhu is formed by nanadravya (extracts of many substances) , hence it is yogavahi (acts following the drug/substance with which used) [6]

(6)Group inclusion (bargikarana)- Madhu is discussed under the group Ikshuvarga (sugarcane and its products)[7]

B]Facts available in Susruta Samhita -

(1)Properties of honey - Madhu is madhura (sweet), kashaya anurasa (astringent) , ruksha (dry), shita (cold) , agnideepana (increases digestive capacity), barnya (increases the body colour) , swaryya (makes the voice clear) , laghu (light), sukumarakara (increases beauty and smoothness) , lekshana (produces scraping of accumulated dosha) , hridya (cardiogenic), bajikarana (aphrodisiac) , sandhana (helps in healing), shodhana (causes purification of the body) , ropana (healer), sangrahi (produces stasis) , chakshusya (beneficial for the eyes) , prasada (produces cleanliness) , sukshmamarganusari (has the property to enter even in the minute channels of the body), pitta-shleshma-meda-meha-hikka-swasa-kasa-atisara-chardi-trishna-krimi-vishaprasamana (pacifies pitta , kafa , fat , urinary problems , hiccough , breathing difficulty , cough , loose motion , vomiting , thirst , worm infestation , poisoning states) , hladi (produces happiness) , tridoshaprasamana (pacifies tridosha). It is laghu (light) , hence kafaghna (pacifies kafa) . It is also picchila (slimy) , Madhura (sweet) and Kashaya (astringent) , hence vata – pittaghna (pacifies vata and pitta)[8]

(2)Types of honey (Madhubheda) – Madhu is of 8 types as – pauttika , bhramara , kshoudra , makshika , chatra , arghya , audyalaka and dala[9]

(3)Quality of honey (Madhuguna) – Pauttika – ruksha(dry) , ushna (hot) and prepared by savisha makshika (poisonous insects) from vishakta pushparasa (poisonous flower juice) . It is vata-asrik-pittakrit (increases vata , rakta and pitta) , chedi (causes scraping of the accumulated harmful products) , bidahi (causes burning sensation) , madakrit (produces affect on intelligence) [10]

Bhramara madhu – picchila (unactuous) , swadu (sweet) , guru (heavy) [11]

Kshoudra madhu – shitala (cold) , laghu (light), lekshana (produces scraping of the accumulated harmful substances) [12]

Makshika madhu – laghutara (lighter than the previous one) , ruksha (dry) , pravara (better) and beneficial specially in swasaroga (diseases with breathing difficulty) [13]

Chatra madhu – swadupaka (becomes sweet after digestion) , guru (heavy), hima (cold), picchila (slimy) , raktapittajit (cures bleeding disorders) , switra-meha-krimighna (cures leukoderma , urinary diseases , worm infestations) . It is said to be superior than all other types in its guna [14]

Arghya madhu - Atichakshusya (most beneficial for the eyes) , param kafa – pittahara (best pacifier of kafa and pitta) , kashayarasa (astringent taste), katu vipaka (pungent after digestion) , balya (increases strength) , tiktarasa (bitter in taste) , not ativatakrit (not excessive vitiator of vata) [15]

Auddalaka madhu – Ruchikara (increases the sense of taste) , swaryya (increases clarity of voice) , kushtha and vishapaha (cures skin diseases and poisoning)[16]

Dala madhu – Kashayarasa (Astringent in taste) , ushna (hot), amla (sour) , pittakrit (increases pitta) , katupaki (after digestion becomes pungent) , chardi - meha prasamana (cures vomiting and urinary problems) and ruksha (dry in quality) [17]

Naba madhu (new honey) is vringhaniya (nutritious) , natishleshmahara (slightly kafahara) and sara (has the capacity to spread) [18]

Purana madhu (old honey)is medanashaka (causes loss of excess fat) , sthauyanashaka (cures obesity) , grahi (helps in stasis) and atilekhana (have strong capacity to scrap the excess accumulation of unwanted substances in the system / channels) [19]

Pakwa madhu (honey collected from matured bee hive) is doshatrayahara (pacifies tridosha) [20]

Ama madhu (honey collected by breaking new bee hive) is amla (sour) and tridoshakrit (causes vitiation of thidosha) [21]

(4)Speciality of honey (yogavahitwa) - Honey is prepared by mixture of nanadravya (many types of substances) . Hence it acts in a broad spectrum of diseases when used with different types of yoga (medicine) . So it is considered as “yogavahi” [22]

(5)Heat and honey - Honey is a mixture of nanadravyarasagunaveeryavipakaviruddha pushparasa (juice of different substances , taste , quality , potency and sometimes even of opposite nature)and also prepared by the action of savisha makshika (poisonous insects / flies) . Hence it should not be exposed or mixed with ushna upachara or ushna Avastha (hot transformation procedure or hot situation)[23]

Madhu is produced from number of visha (poison) by vishakta madhumakshika (poisonous bees) . Hence it has birodha with ushnata (incompatibility with heat) . If used in ushnarta , ushna avastha and ushna kala (heat , hot situation or hot season) it can kill the user as visha (poison) . Again it is ushnaviruddha (incompatible with heat) due to its saukumaryya (smoothness) , saitya (coldness) and nana aushadhirasa sambhavata (produced from many juices with medicinal property) . It is also harmful if used with antariksha jala (rain water)[24]

Madhu is used in ushna Avastha (hot form) in vamana karma (to induce vomiting) . Since , in this use , it is not metabolised and not remains inside the body (comes out as vomitus) hence it is not harmful / contra indicated [25]

(6)Indigestion due to honey (madhujanya ajirna) - If madhu is used in excessive quantity it may produce "ama"(indigestion) . In all states of ama ushnakriya (application of heat in direct or indirect way) is to be done . But , in this situation ushnakriya is contra indicated . Hence ama due to madhu is very difficult to treat , even it may become fatal [26]

(7)Categorisation of honey (varga) - It is discussed under the heading Madhuvarga [27]

C]Facts available in Ashtanga Hridaya -

(1)Qualities of honey (Madhuguna) – Honey is chakshushya (helpful for the eyes) , chedi (reduces the accumulated dosha) , tritshleshmabishahidhmaasrapittanut (cures thirst , kafaja roga , poison , hiccough , bleeding disorders) , mehakusthakrimiccharidswaskaasatisarajit (cures urinary problems , skin diseases , worm infestations , vomiting , respiratory disorders , cough , diarrhoea) , vranashodhanasandhanaropana (causes cleaning of abscess , helps in healing of the fractures , ulcer etc.) , vatala (causes aggravation of vata) . It is ruksha (dry) , kashaya (astringent) madhura (sweet)[28]

(2)Heat and honey (ushnamadhu) – If honey is used in hot state , by an individual exposed to heat or mixed with hot additives (Ushnam ushnartam , ushneyuktang , ushnaih nihanti tat (madhu)) [29]

(3)Use of hot honey (ushna madhu prayoga) – Hot honey is not contra indicated or harmful when used for induced vomiting and enema for cleaning as it is not digested and returns from the system after some time (pracchardane niruhe madhu ushnang na nibaryate) [30]

D]Facts available in modern resources –

Search of the modern informations on honey shows the following results –

(1)Honey is a sweet , viscous substance which is made by several species of bees [31]

(2)Honey bees produce honey by gathering and refining the sugary secretions of plants , primarily floral nectar or the secretions of other insects (honeydew of aphids) [32]

(3)Refinement of the constituents of honey takes place within the individual bees through regurgitation , enzymatic activity and water evaporation to make the ultimate product thick and viscous [33]

(4)Honey for human use is collected from wild bee colonies or from the hives of domesticated bee [34]

(5)The sweetness of honey is due to presence of monosaccharide fructose and glucose in high concentration [35]

(6)One standard tablespoon (approx. 14ml) of honey can provide 180 kilojoules(43 kilocalori) of food energy [36]

(7)Due to high concentration of sugar and acidic pH many microorganisms cannot grow in it [37]

(8)Honey is suitable for long term storage . It is easily assimilated even after long preservation [38]

(9)An enzyme available in the stomach of the bees attributes in long life of honey [39]

- (10)Honey is used as food and fermented beverage mainly [40]
- (11)The physical properties of honey is dependant upon water content , type of flora used to produce , temperature , proportion of the specific sugar content etc. [41]
- (12)Honey contains electrolytes as acids and minerals [42]
- (13)Honey is classified basically depending upon its source [43]
- (14)Honey basically supplies energy (1,270 kJ – 300 kcal per 100gm) . It contains no fat [44]
- (15)Honey contains fructose (51%) , glucose (44%) , galactose , maltose and sucrose [45]
- (16)Researches prove the efficacy of honey in a good number of situations like – burn , skin injury , antibacterial , cough , in the situations of side effects of radiation / chemotherapy , allergic conjunctivitis and constipation [46]
- (17)Honey may show adverse effects or interaction in combination with excessive consumption , existing diseases . drugs etc. [47]

DISCUSSION –

The observations of the present study can be discussed as follows –

- (1)Charaka , Susruta and Bagbhata (Ashtanga Hridaya) discuss in detail on madhu (honey)
- (2)From the observation it becomes clear that the description of Susruta available in Susruta Samhita is more detail which reflects the broad spectrum of the study area of the scholar .
- (3)Ayurvedic scholars have precisely but scientifically discuss the property , use , indications etc. in detail which have scope of further study and research . Even it is indicated in a good number of urinary problems including Diabetes mellitus (madhumeha) .
- (4)Classification of honey basing upon the type of it's producer honey bee (madhumakshika) . Charaka describes 4 types whereas Susruta says it as of 8 types . The difference in the number needs extensive study and analysis . During the present study modern classification of honey basing upon the type of honey bee is not found by the author .
- (5)It is also said by the Ayurvedic authors that , each type of honey bee produces honey of different property and therapeutic importance . An analysis of the classical types of honey with special reference to ingredients is important to establish the difference among these types .
- (6)With regards to the therapeutic utilities of honey similarity in the concept of the Ayurvedic scholars and the modern studies can easily be established . Astonishingly the indications of honey for therapeutic purposes mentioned in the Ayurvedic classics seems to be more extensive .
- (7)The study shows that , there are many facts on honey in the Ayurvedic classics specially in Charaka Samhita and Susruta Samhita which needs extensive study and research to understand the facts behind their concepts .
- (8)Most of the concepts on honey mentioned in the Ayurvedic classics seems to have scope of study basing upon the traditional experiences of it's use .
- (9)A modern analytical study of the changes occur in relation to change of temperature can be considered important to accept / discard the concept of the Ayurvedic scholars about the poisonous effect of honey when used in hot form , with hot substance , hot weather (summer

season) , user exposed to heat . In the present study the author has not got fact to support the concept . But there is an experience of the author of getting good result by prohibiting use of honey with hot water in a patient of unexplained complaints of weakness and pain .

SUMMARY –

The present study can be summerised as follows –

(1)Honey has been considered and used since long past by the human society as a traditional food , medicine , preservative , beverage etc.

(2)In the Ayurvedic classics it is evident that, the scholars and researchers of ancient Indian health science kept serious and cordial concern with the valuable gift “honey” with special reference to it’s property , composition , quality , therapeutic use and efficacy , indications , contra-indications , adverse effects , interaction with it’s additives etc. which are very interesting and informative with a number of secrets behind it .

(3)The author of the present article tried from his best to explore the scientific justification of the informations on honey available in the Ayurvedic classics . But , in most of the references, not got authentic information .

(4)The researchers , academicians and scientists of modern era are requested to take necessary study , research and activities to prove the authenticity of the Ayurvedic concepts on honey appropriately .

CONCLUSION –

As concluding remark it can be said that , our ancestors were aware about the nature’s gifts , their appropriate use by understanding the scientific grounds . But the presently available informations are seemed to be brief and not easily understandable . Hence an extensive , systematic study on one of the important gift of the nature “honey (modhu)” should be considered as the demand of the time . A multi disciplinary scientific study on honey can be expected to be a good resource of knowledge on this important nature’s gift .

REFERENCES –

[1] Shashtri Satya Narayana , Charaka Samhita , Prathama bhaga , Edition 4 , 1988 , Sutrasthana , chapter 27 , Sloka 243- 244

[2] Shashtri Satya Narayana , Charaka Samhita , Prathama bhaga , Edition 4 , 1988 , Sutrasthana , chapter 27 , Sloka 245

[3] Shashtri Satya Narayana , Charaka Samhita , Prathama bhaga , Edition 4 , 1988 , Sutrasthana , chapter 27 , Sloka 246

[4] Shashtri Satya Narayana , Charaka Samhita , Prathama bhaga , Edition 4 , 1988 , Sutrasthana , chapter 27 , Sloka 247

[5] Shashtri Satya Narayana , Charaka Samhita , Prathama bhaga , Edition 4 , 1988 , Sutrasthana , chapter 27 , Sloka 248

[6] Shashtri Satya Narayana , Charaka Samhita , Prathama bhaga , Edition 4 , 1988 , Sutrasthana , chapter 27 , Sloka 249

- [7] Shashtri Satya Narayana , Charaka Samhita , Prathama bhaga , Edition 4 , 1988 ,
Sutrasthana , chapter 27 , Sloka 243 -249
- [8] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 , 1987 ,
Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 132
- [9] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 , 1987 ,
Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 133
- [10] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 , 1987 ,
Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 134
- [11] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 , 1987 ,
Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 135(1)
- [12] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 , 1987 ,
Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 135(2)
- [13] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 , 1987 ,
Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 137
- [14] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 , 1987 ,
Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 137
- [15] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 , 1987 ,
Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 138
- [16] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 , 1987 ,
Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 139(1)
- [17] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 , 1987 ,
Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 139(2)
- [18] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 , 1987 ,
Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 140(2)
- [19] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 , 1987 ,
Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 141(1)
- [20] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 ,
1987 , Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 141(2)
- [21] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 ,
1987 , Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 141(2)
- [22] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 ,
1987 , Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 142
- [23] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 ,
1987 , Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 143
- [24] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 ,
1987 , Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 144 - 145

[25] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 , 1987, Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 146

[26] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 , 1987, Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 147

[27] Shastri Ambikadutta , Susrutasamhita of Maharsi Susruta , Part I , Edition 6 , 1987, Sutrasthana , chapter 45 , sloka 132 -147

[28] Sastri Hari Sadasiva , Ashtanga Hridaya of Vagbhata , Edition 2022 , Sutrasthana , Chapter 5 , Sloka 51, 52, 53(1)

[29] Sastri Hari Sadasiva , Ashtanga Hridaya of Vagbhata , Edition 2022 , Sutrasthana , Chapter 5 , Sloka No. 53(2)

[30] Sastri Hari Sadasiva , Ashtanga Hridaya of Vagbhata , Edition 2022 , Sutrasthana , Chapter 5 , Sloka 51-54

[31] Wikipedia <https://en.wikipedia.org> accessed on 21st April, 2026 , 11.20 P.M

[32] Wikipedia <https://en.wikipedia.org> accessed on 21st April, 2026 , 11.25 P.M

[33] Wikipedia <https://en.wikipedia.org> accessed on 21st April, 2026 , 11.30 P.M

[34] Wikipedia <https://en.wikipedia.org> accessed on 21st April, 2026 , 11.32 P.M

[35] Wikipedia <https://en.wikipedia.org> accessed on 21st April, 2026 , 11.35 P.M

[36] Wikipedia <https://en.wikipedia.org> accessed on 21st April, 2026 , 11.38 P.M

[37] Wikipedia <https://en.wikipedia.org> accessed on 21st April, 2026 , 11.40 P.M

[38] Wikipedia <https://en.wikipedia.org> accessed on 21st April, 2026 , 11.42 P.M

[39] Wikipedia <https://en.wikipedia.org> accessed on 21st April, 2026 , 11.45 P.M

[40] Wikipedia <https://en.wikipedia.org> accessed on 21st April, 2026 , 11.47 P.M

[41] Wikipedia <https://en.wikipedia.org> accessed on 21st April, 2026 , 11.50 P.M

[42] Wikipedia <https://en.wikipedia.org> accessed on 21st April, 2026 , 11.52 P.M

[43] Wikipedia <https://en.wikipedia.org> accessed on 21st April, 2026 , 11.57 P.M

[44] Wikipedia <https://en.wikipedia.org> accessed on 22nd April, 2026 , 12.05 A.M

[45] Wikipedia <https://en.wikipedia.org> accessed on 22nd April, 2026 , 12.10 A.M

[46] Wikipedia <https://en.wikipedia.org> accessed on 22nd April, 2026 , 12.20 A.M

[47] Wikipedia <https://en.wikipedia.org> accessed on 22nd April , 2026 , 12.30 A.M

X-----X